

Effect of Mentoring Technique in Reducing Aggressive Behaviour Among Secondary School Students in Enugu State

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Abstract

Aggression on the part of students at the secondary school level is an anti-social behaviour that could result to violence and abuse of persons or property. It is considered to be the most common and widespread emotional manifestation of many students at all levels of education. This study therefore investigated the effect of mentoring technique in reduction of aggressive behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu North Local Government of Area. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. Quasi-experimental design was adopted for the study. A sample of 120 SS1 and JSS1 students was drawn from a total population of 468 students with aggressive behaviour. The instrument for data collection was Aggressive Behaviour Questionnaire. Statistical mean and Analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA) were used for data analysis. Results from the study showed that mentoring technique was significantly effective in reducing aggressive behaviour among secondary school students. The results also showed that mentoring technique was more effective in reducing aggressive behaviour among female and older secondary school students than their male and younger counterparts respectively. However, the finding of the study revealed that the difference in the effectiveness of mentoring technique in reducing aggressive behaviour among the students based on gender and age was not significant. It was recommended among others, that mentoring technique should be adopted by school guidance counsellors and other allied professionals as an effective treatment for helping students with aggressive behaviour to improve their life skills by becoming a better individual in the society and also living peacefully with their fellow students in the school environment and outside the school.

Key words: *Mentoring, Technique, Reduction, Aggressive behaviour, Students*

Introduction

Educational institutions all over the world are seen as formal settings for character and life skills development of students at various levels. The ability of a student to relate freely and friendly with peers and teachers qualifies a student to fully embrace and maintain good interpersonal relationship both in the school and outside school environment. Any behaviour that can negatively affect a student's interpersonal

relationship will invariably affect the integral development of such student. Aggressive behaviour is one of the major factors that cause disruption in the interpersonal dynamics of teaching and learning in the school environment. Aggressive behaviour occurs in many forms, and can be either verbal or physical. According to Lorenzo (2016), aggressive behaviour is a deliberate destructive behaviour directed towards persons or groups of persons, objects, or towards itself, causing physical or mental suffering which may even result in death. Also, aggressive behaviour can lead to destruction of objects, if aggression is directed towards oneself; it can cause self-injury or suicidal action.

In the opinion of Cristea (2011), aggressive behaviour may be direct or indirect; physical, mental, sexual, verbal; spontaneous or premeditated; provoked or unprovoked. In secondary schools today, the use of weapons such as; knives, dagger, bottles and axes for fighting among students is common especially during inter-class fights and inter-school sports competitions. Many students tend to sustain injuries during such clashes. Physical fight between one student and the other including bullying are frequent occurrences in secondary schools. The use of disdainful and humiliating words by some students on their fellow students is also a form of aggressive act.

The term aggressive behaviour is used widely to refer to any of the following acts; physical fight or assault, verbal threats or hostile statements, threatening gestures, tantrums, self-destructions and destruction of persons or property. Many authors such as Zirpoli, Krache and Myers (2015) have defined aggression from their personal point of view. Zirpoli (2008) defined aggression as any act intended to cause harm, pain or injury in another person. Myers (2016) defined aggression as physical or verbal behaviour that is intended to hurt someone. Similarly, aggressive behaviour has been defined as any behaviour directed towards another person that is carried out with the proximate intent to cause physical or psychological harm (Krahé 2013). The use of disdainful and humiliating words by some students on their fellow students is also a form of aggressive behaviour. The similarity in these definitions implies that aggression is a willful act that is meant to cause pain or injury on another person. A close observation on these definitions shows that aggressive behaviour has no single definition.

According to Shekarey, Ladani and Rostami (2013), aggressive behaviour is common in schools such as fight among students, destruction of school property, bullying of junior students by senior students in secondary schools. In most secondary schools, aggressive behaviour among students seems to have become a routine that seeks to enthrone violence as a quasi-social culture of students. Aluede (2011) noted that violence in schools was an issue that had become more prominent in the last few years, as news articles about violent deeds within the school settings are now on the increase. Considering the dangers associated with aggressive acts, Paul and Iwuama, (2011) observed that aggression is one of the major worldwide concerns in all segments of the society. The involvement of secondary school students in violent activities is prevalent in almost every African community. Violent crimes among students rose at an alarming rate with juvenile arrests for Violent Crime Index offences such as murder, forcible rape, robbery, aggravated assault are on the increase every day around the globe.

According to Barth, Dunlap, Dane, Lochman and Wells (2014) a good number of factors can contribute to the causes of aggressive behaviour in students. In their opinion exposure to grade school classrooms with many aggressive members may increase the risk of persistent aggressive behaviour problems. According to the study of Robertson, Daffer & Bucks (2015) on psychology of violence, unexpressed emotions could lead to violence as participants who could not express their emotions properly were identified with more extensive histories of aggression than those who could express their emotions freely.

Observational learning is another factor that plays a major role in the development of various knowledge structures that supports aggression since non-aggressive individuals can imitate aggressive individuals through mere observation. Ordinarily, children and students tend to observe closely the people around them and surprisingly can learn how to act aggressively from their aggressive role models. Therefore, one may say that children aggressive nature can be influenced strongly by how aggressive their

parents or peer group members are. Hill and Nathan (2008), made an important observation by saying that as children grow, their aggressive behaviour and beliefs as adults are correlated with the amount of inter-parental violence they witnessed in their homes when they were children. This suggested that the pain of rejection could lead to anger, frustration and eventually aggression. On considering some of the causes of aggression, Sheehan and Watson (2008) are of the opinion that a certain relationship exists between aggression and punishment with each stimulating the other. The opinion of Sheehan and Watson portrays the fact that the use of punishment tend to increase the rate of aggression in children instead of minimizing it. Their opinion is suggesting that other means of controlling aggressive behaviour should be sought to help in reducing the rate of aggressive acts among young persons.

One possible reason for this is that children do not like violence and will avoid bullies and people whom they regard as dangerous and prospective candidates of aggression. As a result, rejected aggressive students often seek out other rejected aggressive peers, or they withdraw from peers altogether and spend their time on isolated activities such as watching television or playing video games. In either case, these students are likely to become even more aggressive because they are surrounded by aggressive role models. The U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2016 asserts that relatively little is known about the effectiveness of many of the programs currently in use in schools for curbing aggressive behaviour of students. Due to the growing concern for the social and emotional needs of children and adolescent victims of aggression, the role of teachers and guidance counsellors has been widened. As a result of increase in the rate of aggressive cases in secondary schools, teachers are often left to learn how to prevent aggression on their own and often times they do so out of frustration and anger towards aggressive students.

According to Driscoll, Holt and Hunter (2008), aggressive and violent behaviour can be prevented by using mentoring technique to teach children strategies they can use to help them avoid such behaviour. Children could be taught skills that can promote social skills like compassion, tolerance, problem solving skills, conflict resolution, anger management and empathy. As a matter of fact, aggressive behaviour among secondary school students remains an issue of concern among stakeholders in education because schools are institutions that are only designed for teaching and learning. The teaching and learning can only successfully take place in an environment that is devoid of intimidation, harassment, insecurity and fear. Aluede (2011) found that four in every five secondary school participants (78%) reported being bullied and 85% of the respondents admitted bullying others at least once. In a similar study by Aluede 62.4% of the respondents have been victims of bullying, while 29.6% indicated that they have bullied others.

In the same vein, a study conducted by Asamu (2017), bullying behaviour was found to be more peculiar to junior secondary school students (22.5%), while 21% of the male students had bullied others. Also, a research conducted by Omoteso (2010) showed that prevalence of aggression among students was 67.2%. Thus 88.1% has been bullied while 33.1% were bullies. There is also an indication that there is gender difference in aggressive behaviour among secondary school students. Report from the work of Onukwufor (2013) showed that the prevalence of physical aggression among adolescent secondary school students was 20.8%. In group classification, it was found that physical aggression was more prevalent among male (25.7%) than among female (15%). The result showed that 48.3% (174) of the adolescent secondary school students proved to be verbally aggressive. The categorization showed that 51.7% (87) of the male students reported to be verbally aggressive, while 45 % (81) of the female students were found to be verbally aggressive. Similarly, Asamu (2017) observed that a great deal of aggression is carried out by older students toward younger ones. Asamu further highlighted that mentoring technique is more effective on aggressive behaviour of older students while relaxation technique is more effective on the younger students. Asamu further highlighted that aggression is peculiar to JSS than SSS. In addition, students in middle grades of 6 and 8 are reported of having greater frequency of aggression than the students in grades 9 and 10 in USA (Omoteso 2010).

In spite of all these laudable efforts by previous researchers in other to reduce the frightening effect of aggressive behaviour among students; aggressive behaviour still remains a challenge that poses a serious

threat to many students population. Consequent upon this, the present study was initiated to explore a counselling technique that could possible help to solve the problem of aggressive behaviour among students. Hence, this study sought to determine the effect of mentoring technique on aggressive behaviour among secondary school students.

Mentoring according to Tucker (2009) is a supportive learning relationship between an individual (the mentor) who shares his or her knowledge, experience, and insights with another less experienced person (the learning associate) who is willing and ready to benefit from this exchange. Mentoring produces an opportunity for a mentee to observe and listen to a person who is interestingly of significance to him or her. Similarly, mentoring is an activity that engages either an individual or a group of persons in an interactive session that is geared towards achieving certain developmental goals. It has been linked to a good number of benefits for the young people especially in the area of social-emotional development, youth's perception of parental relationships and better prospects for moving on to higher education. Ultimately, it connects a young person to personal growth and development as well as social and economic opportunities. The technique is also designed to develop skills and knowledge of staff to enable them carry out their roles as teachers with confidence, commitment and enthusiasm. It also provides an avenue for staff to learn and develop both professionally and personally in a safe and supportive environment.

Mentoring is often one component of a program that involves other elements, such as tutoring or life skills training and coaching. The supportive, healthy relationships formed between mentors and mentees are both immediate and long-term and contributes to a host of benefits for mentors and mentees. National Mentoring Resource Centre America maintains that mentoring as a programme can be used in treatment of delinquent and aggressive behaviour as well as problems associated with depression and anxiety.

Odebunmi (2017) said that creating mentoring initiative would help the adolescent student to work on his behavioural deficiencies, adding that those mentors would help to protect and guide these students to remain focused and avoid the pitfalls of negative influences. Mentoring gives young people the guarantee that there is someone who cares about them, who also assures them that they are not alone in dealing with day-to-day challenges, and makes them to have great sense of belonging. Mentoring relationship have powerful positive effects on young people in personal, academic, and professional situations. In the view of Justin (2018), he said that the Chronicle of Evidence Based Mentoring mentioned in his work are related to the following; to help young people develop intrapersonal competencies that involve self-management, emotion and behaviour regulation especially in the area of impulse control, to help young people develop interpersonal competencies that include expressing information to others as well as understanding and interpreting messages and information received from others and to respond appropriately to a piece of information received from others. Similarly, mentors would help young people to develop Cognitive competencies which include thinking, reasoning and other skills that are needed in the relationship with other people. Ubanga, Nwadiuwe and Iyayi (2014) investigated the effectiveness of mentoring technique when compared with relaxation technique. It was discovered that Mentoring proved more effective in the modification of adolescents' aggressive behaviour. There are still notable researchers who have used this technique in reduction of aggressive behaviour. Meyerson (2013) used mentoring technique on youths with emotional and behavioural problems among secondary school students. Also, Wood and Mayo-Wilson (2012) used mentoring technique in school based mentoring for adolescents with deviant behaviours in secondary school.

Aggressive behaviour among students has been found to be significantly correlated with gender. Nelson and Abudul (2015) reported that aggressive behaviour is more present in male students than their female counterpart. Similarly, Sufiana and Malik (2012) found that female students suffer from aggressive behaviour more than the male students. However, Acker, Grant and Henry (2014) had a contrary view on

the gender difference in aggressive behaviour. They reported that male students are more prone to aggressive behaviour than their female counterpart.

In the recent past, a good number of researchers have investigated the effects and effectiveness of different psychological techniques in reducing aggressive behaviour, yet the problem still remains a source of worry to parents, educationists and to students' as well. Due to high increase in the rate of aggressive behaviour among students, there is still the need to find more possible strategies to help students get out of aggressive behaviour because of the inherent dangers which are associated with it. Therefore, this study sets out to ascertain the effect of Mentoring technique on aggressive behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the effect of mentoring technique on aggressive behaviour of secondary school students when compared to those treated with conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest mean scores?
2. What are the differences in the effects of mentoring technique on aggressive behaviour of male and female secondary school students using their pretest and posttest mean scores.
3. What are the differences in the effects of mentoring technique on aggressive behaviour of secondary school students based on their age using their pretest and posttest mean scores.

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 levels of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the effect of mentoring techniques on aggressive behaviour of secondary school students when compared to those treated with conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest aggressive behaviour mean scores.
2. There is no significant difference in the pretest and posttest aggressive behaviour mean scores of male and female secondary school students treated with mentoring technique.
3. There is no significant difference in the pretest and posttest aggressive behaviour mean scores of secondary school students treated with mentoring technique based on their age.

Method

This study is a quasi-experimental research. According to Nworgu (2015), quasi-experiment is an experiment where a random assignment of subjects to experimental and control groups is not possible. In this case, intact or pre-existing groups are used. According to Asgari and Nunes (2011), quasi-experiment research is conducted in a natural setting rather than laboratory conditions, but in this design, variables are isolated, controlled and manipulated. Many quasi experimental methods are available but the one that was used for this study was a non-randomised pretest-posttest and control group design.

The study was conducted in Enugu State which is one of the states in South Eastern part of Nigeria. The population of the study is 468 junior and senior secondary school students facing high level of aggressive behaviour. The population of this study was specifically drawn from JSSI students and SSI students from all the co-educational secondary schools in Enugu North Local Government (Source: Enugu State post primary school services commission 2017/2018). There are nine (9) public secondary schools in Enugu North Local government (4 co-educational and 5 single sex schools) The four co-educational secondary schools has a total population of 2,377 for JSS1 and SS1 students. The sample size of this study was 120 aggressive students. This comprised of all SS1 and JSS1 students chosen from the three coeducational secondary schools selected for the study. The sample size was derived from the population

of 468 students with high aggressive behaviour scores from three coeducational secondary schools in Enugu north local government area using purposive sampling technique.

The instrument adopted and used for measuring of student's aggression was Aggression Behaviour Questionnaire (ABQ). The instrument was originally developed by Buss and Warren (2000) but revalidated in Nigeria by Akpan in 2010. ABQ has been adapted to Nigerian setting and have been used extensively in Nigeria. The Aggression Behaviour Questionnaire is a self report psychometric scale which was developed to measure individual's aggressive conduct as it relates to social setting, and peers. The test is two pages and contains thirty four items. The instrument is on a five point scale, ranging from 1=Not at all like me; 2=A little like me; 3=Somewhat like me; 4=Very much like me;5=Completely like me. The researcher adopted the instrument.

The Aggression Behaviour Questionnaire for this study has two sections: A and B. Section A is an introductory part that solicited for the bio-data of the respondents and section B is directed towards measuring students level of aggression. The respondents were required to indicate by ticking (✓) how often they experience certain feelings, thought and actions. All responses for the thirty four items on Aggression Behaviour Questionnaire were summated to yield a total score of one hundred and seventy. The instrument for data collection has both direct and reverse scoring pattern. Each response was scored according to the specification on the ABQ manual. Scores that were above the norm 116 indicated the presence of aggressive behaviour while scores below this was an indication of having no problem.

Buss and Warren in 2000 obtained a coronbach alpha internal consistency reliability 0.81 coefficient. In Nigeria Akpan (2010) used Aggression Behaviour Questionnaire Inventory to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.82. This study is adopting the Nigeria version whose reliability coefficient of 0.82. has been determined, and there was no need for further reliability estimation.

All the senior secondary (SS1) and junior secondary school (JSS1) students from all the coeducational secondary schools were given the Aggression Behaviour Questionnaire Inventory to complete. The researchers and six well trained research assistants went around the secondary schools to distribute 2,337 copies of the questionnaire. Participants were met in their individual classes and were given the instrument ABQ to respond to the items. The researchers gave the students an introductory instruction on how to complete the questionnaire. The nature of the student's responses and the purpose for which it was given to them were clearly explained to the students. The researchers with the research assistants properly assisted and guided the students on how to respond to the questionnaire. The questionnaire sheets were collected from the students immediately they finished responding to the items and were handed over to the researchers for scoring. Thus this was regarded as the pretest.

Each response was scored according to the specification on the ABQ manual. Scores that were above the norm 116 indicated high level of aggressive behaviour and scores below this showed no problem with aggressive behaviour. This enabled the researchers to identify aggressive students. These scores from the first administration of the questionnaire made up the pretest. A special request was then made to the school principal for provision of adequate and conducive classroom for the administration of the treatment. After the six weeks experimental treatment and control group conventional group counselling, the instrument, ABQ was re-administered on the students and this was regarded as the posttest. The responses were collected, scored and analyzed to determine statistical difference between the experimental and control groups.

Results

Table 1: Pretest and Posttest aggression mean scores of secondary school students treated using mentoring technique and those treated with conventional counselling

N=116

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Mentoring	40	131.65	87.90	43.75	Effective
Control	40	133.08	118.10	14.98	

Table 1 indicates that the secondary school students treated with mentoring technique had pretest aggression mean score of 131.65 and posttest mean score of 87.90 with lost mean 43.75 while those in the control group who were treated with conventional counselling had pretest aggression mean score of 133.08 and posttest mean score of 118.10 with lost mean 14.98. With posttest mean score of 87.90 which is less below the norm of 116, mentoring technique is effective in reducing secondary school students' aggression.

Table 2: Pretest and Posttest mean aggression scores of male and female students treated with mentoring technique

N=116

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Male	20	130.60	91.45	39.15	
Female	20	132.70	83.75	48.95	More effective

Table 2 reveals that the male students treated with mentoring technique had pretest aggression mean score of 130.60 and posttest mean score of 91.45 with lost mean 39.15 while the female students had pretest aggression mean score of 132.70 and posttest mean score of 83.75 with lost mean 48.95. With lost mean score of 48.95, mentoring technique is more effective in reducing female students' aggression.

Table 3: Pretest and Posttest mean aggression scores of students treated with mentoring technique based on their ages

N=116

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
14 to 15	31	131.74	89.16	42.58	
16 to 17	9	131.33	82.22	49.11	More Effective

In table 3, it was observed that the younger students treated with mentoring technique had pretest aggression mean score of 131.74 and posttest mean score of 89.16 with lost mean 42.58 while the older students had pretest aggression mean score of 131.33 and posttest mean score of 82.22 with lost mean 49.11. With lost mean score of 49.11, mentoring technique is more effective in reducing older students' aggression.

Table 4: ANCOVA on the posttest aggression mean scores of secondary school students treated using mentoring technique and those treated with conventional counselling

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	18765.317	2	9382.659			
Intercept	4164.399	1	4164.399			
Aggression 1	160.317	1	160.317			
Treatment model	18765.2071		18765.207	62.38	0.000	S
Error	23164.883	79	300.843			
Total	888180.000	82				
Corrected Total	41930.200	81				

Table 4 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 79df denominator, the calculated F is 62.38 with Pvalue of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected. So, there is significant difference in the posttest aggression mean scores of secondary school students treated using mentoring technique and those treated with conventional counselling.

Table 5: ANCOVA on the posttest aggression mean scores of male and female students treated with mentoring technique.

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	1057.757	2	265.439			
Intercept	884.275	1	884.275			
Aggression 1	56.634	1	56.634	0.37	0.548	NS
Error	5823.843	35	166.167			
Total	313828.000	40				
Corrected Total	6877.600	39				

Table 5 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 39df denominator, the calculated F is 0.37 with Pvalue of 0.548 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the fourth null hypothesis is not rejected. So, there is no significant difference in the posttest aggression mean scores of male and female students treated with mentoring technique.

Table 6: ANCOVA on the posttest aggression mean scores of male and female students treated with mentoring technique.

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	1061.757	2	265.439			
Intercept	994.275	1	994.275			
Aggression 1	53.634	1	53.634			
Gender	61.151	1	61.151	0.368	0.548	NS
Age	311.689	1	311.689	1.876	0.180	NS
Error	5815.84335		166.167			
Total	313828.000	40				
Corrected Total	6877.600	39				

Table 6 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 39df denominator, the calculated F is 1.88 with Pvalue of 0.180 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the fifth null hypothesis is not rejected. So, there is no significant difference in the posttest aggression mean scores of students treated with mentoring technique bases on their ages.

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that mentoring technique was effective on aggressive behaviour of secondary school students as compared to those in the conventional counselling group. Specifically, the finding revealed that students in both mentoring technique and conventional counselling groups exhibited aggressive behaviour before the commencement of the study as measured by their scores on the pre-test. The findings also indicated that the magnitude of the mean difference between the mentoring technique and conventional counselling groups was significant in the post-test.

Moreover, the mentoring technique group reported a significant decrease in aggressive behaviour than the conventional counselling group. This perhaps indicates that the students in the mentoring technique group gained better understanding of their aggressive behaviour as a result of receiving mentoring training. This finding is consistent with prior researches that reported that mentoring technique is effective on aggressive behaviour among secondary school students (Nwaki, 2014; Okey, Peter & David, 2014; Bukola, 2013).

One likely reason for the decrease in aggressive behaviour among students in the mentoring technique treatment group than those in the conventional counselling group might be due to the learning partnership between a more experienced and less experienced individual in which the students were exposed to, during the experiment. Supporting this, Supporters of mentorship argue that early intervention can prevent aggressive behaviour in students, and as a result, many theorize that proper mentorship can alter aggressive behaviours (Satchwell, 2006). Interestingly, although mentoring technique are frequently mentioned as proven to be a practical solution for students with academic and aggressive behaviour problems, effective mentoring program has been found to be characterized by the following essential components: the involvement of personnel who have complementary contact, program coordination with delineated goals and objectives, a target population, specified activities, procedures, training or orientation for mentors and students, quality characteristics of mentors, monitoring, and evaluation.

Another finding of this study is that there was significant gender difference in the effectiveness of mentoring technique on secondary school students' aggression. The result from this study indicated that mentoring technique is more effective in reducing female student's aggression. This suggests that the female students benefited more from mentoring treatment. This finding supports the previous finding by Nwaki (2014) who observed that mentoring technique was more effective in treating female student's aggression. This may be because the female students preferred looking up to mentors who will coach them to be a better individual in society. More so, the students were given equal opportunities to participate in the experimental activities and were also given equal attention.

However, this result contradicts previous finding by Okey, Peter & David (2014) who reported that male students benefited more during mentoring treatment than their female counterpart. Perhaps, Ubangha, Monday, Basse, Nwadinigwe, Peter, (2014) did not maintain equilibrium of condition between the male and female students during his experiment. The findings revealed that Mentoring was more efficacious than relaxation technique in the modification of aggressive behaviour in adolescent students. These findings were situated within the existing body of knowledge and their implications for Counselling Education were discussed. The results also revealed that there was no significant difference in the effectiveness of treatment of mentoring and relaxation technique on aggressive behaviour among secondary school students. It was also found that there was no significant difference in the effectiveness of mentoring technique based on gender. Based on the findings, this study suggested among others, that counsellors should make effective use of Mentoring and Relaxation in treating students with aggressive behaviour.

Furthermore, the findings of this study also indicated that mentoring techniques was more effective in reducing older student's aggression. It was found that mentoring technique differ in their effectiveness among older and younger students. This suggests that the older students benefitted more from mentoring technique treatment than their younger counterpart. This finding is in agreement with the previous finding by Antoni (2009) who concluded that older students benefitted more from mentoring technique than their younger counterparts. The reason why older students benefitted more from mentoring technique may be because they gain better understand of the interpersonal skill of mentoring and was able to boost their self confidence. Again, mentoring is important, not only because of the knowledge and skills students can learn from mentors, but also because mentoring provides students with aggressive behaviour a personal support that will facilitate treatment of their maladaptive behaviours.

However, it should be noted that this result disagrees with the finding by Bukola (2014) who reported that the younger students benefitted more from mentoring technique treatment. Findings from his study indicated that mentoring technique was more effective in reducing aggression among younger students than relaxation technique. It was also found that the female students benefited more from the mentoring treatment than their male counterpart. Based on the above findings it implies that counselling as a service concerned with helping human beings to develop into appropriate personality that has the capacity to help secondary school students to achieve new critical and rational level of reasoning and functioning is very important and should be maintained. Counselling is therefore, expected to help in managing behavioural problems in schools.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study and the discussions that followed, it was concluded that mentoring technique was significantly effective in reducing secondary school students' aggression. It was also concluded that mentoring technique is more effective in reducing female students' aggression, but the difference in effectiveness based on gender was not significant. Finally, the study concluded that mentoring technique is more effective in reducing older students' aggression, than the younger students, but the difference is also not significant.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers made the following recommendations:

1. That mentoring technique should be adopted by school guidance counsellors and other allied professionals as an effective treatment for helping students with aggressive behaviour to improve their life skills by becoming a better individual in the society and also living peacefully with their fellow students in the school environment and outside the school.
2. That counsellor's should provide students with the mentoring tools to defeat the negative self-talk they may experience in their aggressive attitude.
3. Governments and school administrators should give adequate support to counsellors and teachers alike, by providing conducive environment and giving adequate financial support to boost counselling activities in school.
4. Students who are doing well should be celebrated by their schools so that more can be role models for their peers. This is expected to make more students take initiative and be more responsive in making responsible life choices.

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